

High-resolution Proton Resonance Spectra of Dihalobis(2-(arylamino)pyridine)-ruthenium(II) and -osmium(II)[†]

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The high-resolution ¹H nmr spectra of several isomeric 2-(arylamino)pyridine(L) complexes of type ML₂X₂ (M=Ru, Os; X=Cl, Br) are reported and completely assigned. Spectral features diagnostic of geometric structures are delineated and applied to isomers of new complexes.

STRUCTURE and reactivity studies in ruthenium and osmium chemistry of 2-(arylamino)pyridine(L) have received recent attention¹⁻¹⁰. Interesting cases of geometrical isomerism occur^{1,8} in the pseudo-octahedral dihalo species ML₂X₂ (X=Cl, Br). In the present work, we describe the high-resolution ¹H nmr spectra of selected ML₂X₂ complexes including some hitherto unreported species. Complete assignment of spectra is achieved in several cases and features diagnostic of geometric structure are identified.

Experimental

¹H nmr spectra were measured at 270 MHz (Bruker) or 360 MHz (Jeol) in CDCl₃. All chemical shifts are referenced to tetramethylsilane.

The isomers of Ru(pap)₂Cl₂, Ru(tap)₂Cl₂ and Os(tap)₂Br₂ studied in this work were prepared following reported procedures^{1,8,9-9} (pap=2-(phenylamino)pyridine; tap=2-(*m*-tolylamino)pyridine). The ligand dap (2-(*p*-*N,N*-dimethylaminophenylamino)pyridine) was prepared¹¹ by condensing 2-aminopyridine with *p*-nitrosodimethylaniline in dry toluene in the presence of sodium.

Preparation and separation of two isomers of Ru(dap)₂Cl₂: Dinitrogen was passed through a stirred solution of dap (600 mg, 2.68 mmol) in methanol (30 ml) for 15 min. A solution of ruthenium trichloride trihydrate (350 mg, 1.34 mmol) in methanol (20 ml) was added to it. The mixture was heated to reflux for 6 h. A violet solution was obtained which was dried in vacuum. The solid violet mass was subjected to chromatography on a silica gel (B.D.H., 60-120 mesh) column (30×1 cm). Dichloromethane eluted a small green band and from the eluent the tt isomer was isolated (6%) by removal of solvent. A major blue-violet band was then eluted with acetonitrile. The solid mass obtained by removal of solvent in vacuum was suspended in xylene (boiling range 137-142°) (75 ml) and heated to reflux for 9 h in order to convert

any tt isomer present to the tc isomer. The pure tc complex (50%) was obtained by removing the solvent; tt isomer (Found: C, 49.82; H, 4.44; N, 17.97), cc isomer (Found: C, 50.00; H, 4.45; N, 17.92). RuC₂₀Cl₂H₁₆N₄, calcd. for: C, 49.99; H, 4.49; N, 17.95%.

Preparation of tc-Os(dap)₂Cl₂: Dinitrogen was passed through a solution of dap (100 mg, 0.442 mmol) in 2-methoxyethanol (30 ml), and (NH₄)₂OsCl₆ (100 mg, 0.227 mmol) was added. The mixture was heated to reflux for 4 h. The solvent was then evaporated to dryness in vacuum. The violet solid thus obtained was subjected to chromatography on silica gel (B.D.H., 60-120 mesh) column (20×1 cm) using benzene-acetonitrile (9:1) as the eluent. A violet band was eluted out and from it the required complex (59%) was obtained by removal of solvent in vacuum (Found: C, 43.70; H, 3.95; N, 15.71). OsC₂₀Cl₂H₁₆N₄, calcd. for: C, 43.75; H, 3.93; N, 15.70%.

Results and Discussion

Isomerism of ML₂X₂ species: The azopyridines(L) of interest and their abbreviations are shown in structure (1). The pseudo-octahedral

[†] Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

ML_2X_2 species can in principle occur in five geometrically isomeric forms^{1,9} - two and three of these respectively have the MX_2 group in *trans*- and *cis*-geometries. Of the five possible isomers, a maximum of three have been observed in practice. The geometries of N(pyridine), N(pyridine) and N(azo), N(azo) pairs in the observed isomers are *trans-trans* tt (2), *trans-cis* tc (3) and *cis-cis* cc (4).

While $Ru(pap)_2Cl_2$ and $Ru(tap)_2Cl_2$ occur in tt, tc and cc forms⁹, only the tc and cc varieties are observed in the corresponding osmium compounds^{6,7}. The structures of tc- and cc- $Ru(pap)_2Cl_2$ ^{1,2} as well as tc- and cc- $Os(tap)_2Cl_2$ ^{7,13} are accurately known from X-ray work.

The $Ru(dap)_2Cl_2$ and $Os(dap)_2Cl_2$ complexes are reported here for the first time. The ruthenium complex occurs in only two isomeric forms, one green and the other blue-violet. On the other hand, $Os(dap)_2Cl_2$ is found to exist exclusively in one form. Geometrical assignments of these species were achieved on the basis of ir, uv-vis and electrochemical data¹⁴ and more importantly on ¹H nmr data. The latter will be considered in this work.

Spectra of tt and tc isomers of pap and tap complexes: All the complexes display highly

resolved ¹H nmr spectra (a representative case in Fig. 1). Chemical shift and spin-spin splitting (among nearest neighbour protons only) data are in Table 1. Interspectral correlations are displayed schematically in Fig. 2.

The signals from protons of the pyridine rings are readily assigned on the basis¹⁵ of chemical shifts and spin-spin splittings. Thus, the 6-H is a doublet with a relatively low *J* value (~5 Hz). The phenyl ring protons are assigned on a similar basis using substituent-induced change in splitting patterns and chemical shifts as additional indicators. For example, 8-H and 12-H are coincident doublets in *pap* isomers whereas the 8-H signals appear as separate singlet in the corresponding *tap* isomers. Further, the 8-H signals are very significantly shifted to higher fields in going from a *pap* isomer to the corresponding *tap* isomer in accord with the electron releasing character of the methyl substituent¹⁶.

We now consider the consequences of going from the tt to the tc isomer for a given ligand. The major effects are seen in the protons closest to the metal atom. The 6-H is shifted downfield by $\delta \sim 0.4$ and the 8-H and 12-H are shifted upfield by $\delta \sim 0.7$ in going from tt to tc configuration. The two chelate rings are approximately coplanar and orthogonal in the tt and tc isomers, respectively. The larger mutual shielding/deshielding effects and higher spectral spread in the tc isomer is thus qualitatively understandable. An important result is that the 6-H and 8-H, 12-H chemical shifts in tt and tc isomers are of diagnostic value for identification of geometry of the ruthenium complexes: tt isomer: 6-H, δ 8.9; 8-H, 12-H, 7.3-7.6; and tc isomer: 6-H, 9.4; 8-H, 12-H, 6.5-6.8. This result is utilised below for characterisation of the $Ru(dap)_2Cl_2$ isomers.

Isomeric structure of the dap complexes: The green isomer of $Ru(dap)_2Cl_2$ has the 6-H signal at

Fig. 1. ¹H nmr spectrum of aromatic protons of *tc*- $Os(tap)_2Br_2$.

TABLE I—¹H nmr SPECTRAL DATA IN CDCl₃

Compd.	δ (τ)										
	6-H	3-H	4-H	5-H	8-H	9-H	10-H	11-H	12-H	9-Me	10-NMe ₃
tt-Ru(pap) ₂ Cl ₂	8.92 (4.4)	8.60 (7.2)	8.19 (7.6)	7.82 (6.3)	7.54 (8.5)	6.98 (7.8)	7.18 (7.2)	6.98 (7.8)	7.54 (8.5)	—	—
tt-Ru(tap) ₂ Cl ₂	8.91 (4.4)	8.58 (8.3)	8.17 (7.9)	7.79 (5.9)	7.34 (8.5)	—	8.97 (7.8)	6.97 (7.5)	7.40 (7.5)	2.19	—
tc-Ru(pap) ₂ Cl ₂	9.86 (5.4)	8.52 (8.3)	7.99 (7.7)	7.52 (6.6)	6.82 (8.5)	7.11 (7.8)	7.28 (6.8)	7.11 (7.8)	6.82 (8.5)	—	—
tc-Ru(tap) ₂ Cl ₂	9.37 (5.9)	8.52 (7.8)	8.00 (7.8)	7.52 (6.4)	6.60 (8.5)	—	7.08 (7.8)	6.98 (7.6)	6.58 (9.2)	2.14	—
tc-Os(tap) ₂ Br ₂	9.24 (5.9)	8.66 (8.2)	7.69 (7.8)	7.37 (6.6)	6.31 (8.5)	—	6.93 (7.7)	6.35 (7.8)	7.03 (7.6)	2.18	—
tt-Ru(dap) ₂ Cl ₂	8.94 (5.5)	8.43 (8.1)	8.06 (7.9)	7.62 (8.9)	7.60 (9.6)	6.20 (9.2)	—	6.20 (9.2)	7.60 (9.6)	—	3.00
tc-Ru(dap) ₂ Cl ₂	9.51 (5.1)	8.36 (7.8)	7.92 (7.8)	7.44 (6.8)	6.82 (9.3)	6.24 (9.3)	—	6.24 (9.3)	6.82 (9.3)	—	2.94
tc-Os(dap) ₂ Cl ₂	9.11 (6.0)	8.49 (8.0)	7.64 (7.4)	7.33 (6.2)	6.56 (9.1)	6.21 (9.2)	—	6.21 (9.2)	6.56 (9.1)	—	2.92

Fig. 2. Schematic ¹H nmr spectra of complexes: (a) tt-Ru(pap)₂Cl₂, (b) tt-Ru(tap)₂Cl₂, (c) tt-Ru(dap)₂Cl₂, (d) tc-Ru(pap)₂Cl₂, (e) tc-Ru(tap)₂Cl₂, (f) tc-Ru(dap)₂Cl₂, and (g) tc-Os(dap)₂Cl₂. Numbers in the figure indicate the proton number.

δ 8.94 while the 8-H, 12-H doublet occur at 7.60. On the other hand, the corresponding signals in the blue-violet isomer occur at δ 9.51 and 6.82, respectively. Clearly the green isomer has the tt configuration while the blue-violet form is tc. All other properties of the two isomers are in accord¹⁴

with this geometric assignment. Similarly, the only observed isomer Os(dap)₂Cl₂ has tc geometry. We note the large ($\delta \sim 0.8$) upfield shift of 9-H, 11-H signal in going from a pap to the corresponding dap isomer. The strong electron releasing character of the NMe₃ is no doubt responsible.

Spectra of cc isomers : In tt and tc isomers the chelate rings are equivalent due to the presence of two-fold symmetry. The cc isomer is devoid of such symmetry. The nmr spectra of cc complexes are indeed much more complex than those of tt and tc isomers. We shall not consider the details of such spectra any further here since complete and unambiguous assignment of aromatic signals have not been achieved so far. Among Ru(tap)₂Cl₂ isomers, tt and tc display a single 9-Me signal (Table 1) while cc has two such signals (δ 2.21 and 2.41) as expected. Similarly both the observed isomers of Ru(dap)₂Cl₂ have single NMe₂ signal (Table 1).

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References

1. S. GOSWAMI, A. R. CHAKRAVARTY and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1981, 20, 2246.
2. S. GOSWAMI, A. R. CHAKRAVARTY and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 21, 2737.
3. S. GOSWAMI, A. R. CHAKRAVARTY and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1982, 1288.
4. S. GOSWAMI, A. R. CHAKRAVARTY and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 22, 602.
5. S. GOSWAMI, R. N. MUKHERJEE and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1983, 22, 2825.
6. B. K. GHOSH, S. GOSWAMI and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1988, 22, 3358.
7. B. K. GHOSH, A. MUKHOPADHYAY, S. GOSWAMI and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, 23, 4633.
8. R. A. KRAUSE and K. KRAUSE *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, 19, 2600.
9. R. A. KRAUSE and K. KRAUSE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1982, 21, 1714.
10. S. WOLFGANG, T. C. STREKAS, H. D. GAFNEY, R. A. KRAUSE and K. KRAUSE, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1984, 23, 2650.
11. R. W. FAESSINGER and E. V. BROWN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4606.
12. A. SEAL and S. RAY, *Acta Crystallogr., C*, 1984, 40, 929.
13. A. MUKHOPADHYAY and S. RAY, unpublished results.
14. A. MAHAPATRA, B. K. GHOSH, S. GOSWAMI and A. CHAKRAVORTY, unpublished results.
15. B. PÉCCE, "Nuclear Magnetic Resonance in Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1965, p. 174.
16. H. GÜNTHER, "NMR Spectroscopy—An Introduction", Wiley, Chichester, 1980, p. 65.